

ERRATAS MS Access database data entry form: Editorial conventions

Collection:	EXAMPLE	Source:		Source Date:		Filled by:	
Corpus:		Database version: 0				Updated:	

Only source for collection

1. TEXT CHECKED: text Mentioned: text

Text omitted from the letter Mentioned: text omitted

Opening/closing formulas omitted Mentioned: formulas

Datelines omitted Mentioned: datelines

Superscriptions omitted Mentioned: superscriptions

Text NOTES

2. ALLOGRAPHS CHECKED: allographs Mentioned: allographs

Allographs normalized Mentioned: normalized allographs

Long s changed Mentioned: long s

Allograph NOTES

3. SPELLING CHECKED: spelling Mentioned: spelling

Modernized u/v Mentioned: u/v

Minuscule i/j modernized Mentioned: minuscule i/j

Majuscule l/j modernized Mentioned: majuscule l/j

Names normalized Mentioned: normalized names

Modernized ie/ei Mentioned: ie/ei

Modernized -d Mentioned: -d

Long vowels and diphthongs modernized Mentioned: long vowels and diphthongs

Doubled consonants normalized Mentioned: doubled consonants

Spelling NOTES

4. CAPITALIZATION CHECKED: capitalization Mentioned: capitalization

Capitalization modernized Mentioned: modernized capitalization

Capitalization partly normalized Mentioned: normalized capitalization

Normalized pronoun <l> Mentioned: pronoun <l>

Modernized ff/f Mentioned: ff/f

Names capitalized Mentioned: name capitalization

Sentence/paragraph capitalization added Mentioned: sentence capitalization

Capitalization NOTES

5. SPECIAL CHARACTERS AND OBSOLETE GRAPHS CHECKED: special characters and obsolete graphs Mentioned: special characters and obsolete graphs

Special characters and obsolete graphs changed

Changed -es graph Mentioned: -es graph

Changed p-graphs Mentioned: p-graphs

Changed yogh/thorn Mentioned: yogh/thorn

Changed y-as-thorn Mentioned: y-as-thorn

Changed ampersand Mentioned: ampersand

Changed diacritics Mentioned: diacritics

Changed superscript E-shaped <r> Mentioned: E-shaped <r>

Other special characters

Special characters NOTES

6. MACRONS AND ABBREVIATION MARKERS CHECKED: macrons and abbreviation markers Mentioned: macrons and abbreviation markers

Macrons and abbreviation markers omitted Mentioned: omitted macrons and abbreviation markers

Macrons and abbreviation markers normalized Mentioned: normalized macrons and abbreviation markers

Macrons and abbreviation markers NOTES

7. SUPERSCRPTIONS CHECKED: superscripts Mentioned: superscripts

Superscripts lowered Mentioned: lowered superscripts

Some superscripts lowered Mentioned: some lowered superscripts

Otiose superscripts lowered Mentioned: otiose superscripts

Superscripts for dates, numbers and money lowered Mentioned: superscripts for dates, numbers and money

Superscripts NOTES

8. WORD DIVISION CHECKED: word division Mentioned: word division

Word division normalized Mentioned: normalized word division

Suspicious hyphens Mentioned: suspicious hyphens

Separated th-elision Mentioned: th-elision

Prefixes modernized Mentioned: separate prefixes

Word division NOTES

9. MORPHOLOGY CHECKED: morphology Mentioned: morphology

Morphology modernized Mentioned: modernized morphology

Modernized than/then Mentioned: than/then

Modernized h-dropping and hypercorrect Mentioned: h-dropping and hypercorrection

Morphology NOTES

10. ABBREVIATIONS CHECKED: abbreviations Mentioned: abbreviations

Abbreviations changed Mentioned: changed abbreviations

Abbreviations normalized Mentioned: normalized abbreviations

Normalized + marked

Abbreviations expanded Mentioned: expanded abbreviations

Expanded + marked

Abbreviations NOTES

11. PUNCTUATION CHECKED: punctuation Mentioned: punctuation

Punctuation modernized Mentioned: modernized punctuation

Punctuation normalized Mentioned: normalized punctuation

Apostrophes added Mentioned: apostrophes

Hyphens omitted Mentioned: hyphens

Dashes changed Mentioned: dashes

Abbreviation-marking punctuation normalized Mentioned: abbreviation-marking punctuation

Virgules changed Mentioned: virgules

Quotation marks added Mentioned: quotation marks

Punctuation NOTES

12. LAYOUT CHECKED: layout Mentioned: layout

Line breaks changed Mentioned: line breaks

Text alignment changed Mentioned: text alignment

Blanks changed Mentioned: blanks

Marginalia omitted Mentioned: marginalia

Layout NOTES

13. EXTRATEXTUAL/EDITORIAL INFORMATION CHECKED: extratextual/editorial information Mentioned: extratextual/editorial information

Hand changes indicated Mentioned: hand changes

Scribal emendations marked Mentioned: emendations

Scribal errors marked Mentioned: marked scribal errors

Scribal emphasis reproduced Mentioned: scribal emphasis

Underlining reproduced Mentioned: underlining

Manuscript damage noted Mentioned: manuscript damage

Editorial emendations marked Mentioned: not marked editorial emendations

Extratextual/editorial information NOTES

ERRATAS MS Access database data entry form (1/2018): Textual features

Collection: Source: Source Date: Filled by:
 Corpus: Database version: Updated:

Only source for collection

- 1. TEXT** CHECKED: text Applicable: text
- Text omitted from the letter Applicable: text omitted Present: omitted text
 Opening/closing formulas omitted Applicable: formulas Present: formulas
 Datelines omitted Applicable: datelines Present: datelines
 Superscriptions omitted Applicable: superscriptions Present: superscriptions

Text NOTES

- 2. ALLOGRAPHS** CHECKED: allographs Applicable: allographs
- Allographs normalized Applicable: normalized allographs Present: allographs
 Long s changed Applicable: long s Present: long s

Allograph NOTES

- 3. SPELLING** CHECKED: spelling Applicable: spelling
- Modernized u/v Applicable: u/v Present: u/v variation
 Minuscule i/j modernized Applicable: minuscule i/j Present: minuscule i/j variation
 Majuscule I/J modernized Applicable: majuscule I/J Present: majuscule I/J variation
 Names normalized Applicable: normalized names Present: name variation
 Modernized ie/ei Applicable: ie/ei Present: ie/ei variation
 Modernized -d Applicable: -d Present: -d variation
 Long vowels and diphthongs modernized Applicable: long vowels and diphthongs Present: long vowels and diphthongs
 Doubled consonants normalized Applicable: doubled consonants Present: doubled consonants

Spelling NOTES

- 4. CAPITALIZATION** CHECKED: capitalization Applicable: capitalization
- Capitalization modernized Applicable: modernized capitalization
 Capitalization partly normalized Applicable: normalized capitalization Present: variation in capitalization
 Normalized pronoun <I> Applicable: pronoun <I> Present: variation in pronoun <I>
 Modernized ff/F Applicable: ff/F Present: ff/F variation

- 8. WORD DIVISION** CHECKED: word division Applicable: word division
- Word division normalized Applicable: normalized word division Present: variation in word division
 Suspicious hyphens Applicable: suspicious hyphens Present: hyphenated words
 Separated th-elision Applicable: th-elision Present: th-elision
 Prefixes modernized Applicable: separate prefixes Present: separate prefixes

Word division NOTES

- 9. MORPHOLOGY** CHECKED: morphology Applicable: morphology
- Morphology modernized Applicable: modernized morphology
 Modernized than/then Applicable: than/then Present: than/then variation
 Modernized h-dropping and hypercorrection Applicable: h-dropping and hypercorrection Present: h-dropping and hypercorrection

Morphology NOTES

- 10. ABBREVIATIONS** CHECKED: abbreviations Applicable: abbreviations Present: abbreviations
- Abbreviations changed Applicable: changed abbreviations
 Abbreviations normalized Applicable: normalized abbreviations
 Normalized + marked
 Abbreviations expanded Applicable: expanded abbreviations
 Expanded + marked

Abbreviations NOTES

- 11. PUNCTUATION** CHECKED: punctuation Applicable: punctuation
- Punctuation modernized Applicable: modernized punctuation
 Punctuation normalized Applicable: normalized punctuation
 Apostrophes added Applicable: apostrophes Present: apostrophes
 Hyphens omitted Applicable: hyphens Present: hyphens

- Names capitalized Applicable: name capitalization Present: variation in name capitalization
 Sentence/paragraph capitalization added Applicable: sentence capitalization Present: variation in sentence capitalization

Capitalization NOTES

- 5. SPECIAL CHARACTERS AND OBSOLETE GRAPHS** CHECKED: special characters and obsolete graphs
- Special characters and obsolete graphs changed Applicable: special characters and obsolete graphs
 Changed -es graph Applicable: -es graph Present: -es graph
 Changed p-graphs Applicable: p-graphs Present: p-graphs
 Changed yogh/thorn Applicable: yogh/thorn Present: yogh/thorn
 Changed y-as-thorn Applicable: y-as-thorn Present: y-as-thorn
 Changed ampersand Applicable: ampersand Present: ampersand
 Changed diacritics Applicable: diacritics Present: diacritics
 Changed superscript E-shaped <ɹ> Applicable: E-shaped <ɹ> Present: E-shaped <ɹ>

Other special characters

Special characters NOTES

- 6. MACRONS AND ABBREVIATION MARKERS** CHECKED: macrons and abbreviation markers
- Applicable: macrons and abbreviation markers
- Macrons and abbreviation markers omitted Applicable: omitted macrons and abbreviation markers
 Macrons and abbreviation markers normalized Applicable: normalized macrons and abbreviation markers
 Present: macrons and abbreviation markers

Macrons and abbreviation markers NOTES

- 7. SUPERSCRIPTS** CHECKED: superscripts Applicable: superscripts Present: superscripts
- Superscripts lowered Applicable: lowered superscripts
 Some superscripts lowered Applicable: some lowered superscripts
 Otiose superscripts lowered Applicable: otiose superscripts Present: otiose superscripts
 Superscripts for dates, numbers and money lowered Applicable: superscripts for dates, numbers and money Present: superscripts for dates, numbers and money

Superscripts NOTES

- Dashes changed Applicable: dashes Present: dashes
 Abbreviation-marking punctuation Applicable: abbreviation-marking punctuation Present: abbreviation-marking punctuation
 Virgules changed Applicable: virgules Present: virgules
 Quotation marks added Applicable: quotation marks Present: quotation marks

Punctuation NOTES

- 12. LAYOUT** CHECKED: layout Applicable: layout
- Line breaks changed Applicable: line breaks Present: line breaks
 Text alignment changed Applicable: text alignment Present: text alignment
 Blanks changed Applicable: blanks Present: blanks
 Marginalia omitted Applicable: marginalia Present: marginalia

Layout NOTES

- 13. EXTRATEXTUAL/EDITORIAL INFORMATION** CHECKED: extratextual/editorial information
- Applicable: extratextual/editorial information
- Hand changes indicated Applicable: hand changes Present: hand changes
 Scribal emendations marked Applicable: emendations Present: scribal emendations
 Scribal errors marked Applicable: marked scribal errors Present: marked scribal errors
 Scribal emphasis reproduced Applicable: scribal emphasis Present: scribal emphasis
 Underlining reproduced Applicable: underlining Present: underlining
 Manuscript damage noted Applicable: manuscript damage Present: manuscript damage
 Editorial emendations marked Applicable: marked editorial emendations Present: editorial emendations

Extratextual/editorial information NOTES